

SUPPORTING ENTREPRENEURS AND IMPROVING THE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

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***Annotation:** This article discusses how to further reform, further stabilize and grow small businesses and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to what extent the potential of small businesses has grown .*

***Keywords:** business, business entities, real income, employment, GDP, agricultural relations, market economy.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the main ways to strengthen the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its comprehensive development, accelerating the transition to a market economy, in particular, is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. Therefore, a number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted on the development of entrepreneurship, its support by the state, the initiative in private entrepreneurship, its promotion . It is difficult to imagine the fundamental basis of economic and social reforms in our country without entrepreneurship, efficiency and business acumen. The widespread development of free market relations is reflected in people's lives, their lifestyles, spiritual and life skills [1-5]. The support of small business and private entrepreneurship not only provides economic goals related to the sustainable development of the economy, the correction of economic relations, the development of competition and the filling of the consumer market.

In order to further stabilize small business and private entrepreneurship in our country, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree "On

strengthening the protection of private property and guarantees of property rights, entrepreneurial initiatives."

PF-5780 of August 13, 2019 "On additional measures to radically improve the system of organization of support work, as well as to expand the access of business entities to financial resources and production infrastructure" Decree No. PP-4417 of August 13, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the organization of the Agency for Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development under the Ministry of Economy and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan." 1)

ANALYSIS OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE

One of the main goals of building a socially oriented market economy in Uzbekistan is the priority development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country. To achieve this goal, economic reforms have been carried out, and a large institutional framework has been created to enhance its role. These include legal and regulatory documents governing the organization of entrepreneurial activity, non-governmental organizations and enterprises that support entrepreneurs . The establishment of a complex of private entrepreneurship and small business in Uzbekistan is progressing successfully. Small businesses can create jobs independently of the state, that is, without large capital investments, reduce the temporary shortage of existing goods , and even eliminate this shortage completely. In today's society, it is necessary to direct the activities of small businesses to meet the needs of individuals. This is evident in the field of consumer services and consumer goods. Small businesses also play an important role in introducing technology innovations.

Preliminary research in the field of legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity was conducted by lawyer B.Ibratov. He argues that all the actions of the entrepreneur are mainly the analysis of market opportunities, their use, the implementation of innovative ideas, not the traditional class definition of the entrepreneur, which leads to the essence of capitalist exploitation, but its human is a function of his activity in this field, which explains the need to pay attention to its role in society and its social significance [13-19]. The entrepreneur also describes it as a set of organizational,

economic, financial, legal and other economic relations that provide services for reproduction in individual segments of a market economy . (2)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Small business and private entrepreneurship are important factors in economic development, employment and income. Over the past two and a half years, more than 50 decrees and resolutions of the President have been adopted to provide comprehensive support to the representatives of this sphere . In particular, the procedures for state registration of business activities, obtaining various permits and many other services have been simplified . (3) To facilitate this, the Public Service Agency and its local centers have been established. The position of Representative (Business Ombudsman) for the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities was introduced [20-24]. Prime Minister's receptions have been set up in all regions to receive and assist in resolving entrepreneurs' appeals. The State Fund for Entrepreneurship Development under the Cabinet of Ministers has been established, which has been allocated 200 billion soums and \$ 50 million. At the same time, the volume of loans provided by commercial banks to entrepreneurs has increased. Such practical measures are yielding results. Small business provides about 60% of the country's GDP, a third of industrial output, 98% of agricultural output and half of investments. In many regions, 70-90 percent of exports are small businesses . (4)

The main goal of Uzbekistan's economic reforms is to build an open foreign policy, a stable socially oriented market economy, a strong democratic state governed by the rule of law and a civil society. Market reforms in the country are being carried out firmly and consistently. Therefore, the following conditions have been created in the Republic for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship:

1. The registration time for small businesses is 30 minutes. To register as an individual entrepreneur requires only one document, and when registering a small business as a legal entity - two documents .

2. The single tax rate, which is an important factor in creating favorable conditions for the development of small business in almost all industries, is 5% of the volume of goods and services sold. At the same time, the current rate of the single social payment for small businesses is 15 % .
3. Newly established manufacturing enterprises with foreign investment are entitled to apply the rate of taxes and mandatory payments on the day of their registration for five years. From 2018, small businesses with more than 1 hectare of land are set to pay a single land tax.
4. Financial support for small business is provided through the following ways: lending by banks at preferential rates; Guarantee of 50% of loans provided by the State Fund for Entrepreneurship Support for business activities and reimbursement of accrued interest on loans from commercial banks.
5. Business interests are protected by the institution responsible for protecting the rights and legitimate interests of business entities. Unscheduled inspections of small businesses canceled in Uzbekistan as well as business entities were exempted from all types of administrative fines for the first financial and economic offense.
6. Entrepreneurship support centers have been established in all regions of the country in the centers operating under the "single window" principle, providing public services to businesses. "Business incubators" have been set up for start-ups to create their own business plans, provide legal and practical assistance, as well as obtain the necessary information for their activities.
7. Clusters for young entrepreneurs have been established throughout the country through training courses on entrepreneurship for entrepreneurs, implementation of projects on the basis of privatized facilities, allocation of land on a lease basis for 5 years at a zero rate. (5)

At the same time, we need to highlight the problems that prevent small businesses from fully realizing their potential. More than 62% of small business employees are self-employed, while only 16% are small businesses and micro-firms. The lowest employment rates of small enterprises are in Navoi (11.3 %) ,

Kashkadarya (12.4%) and Tashkent region (13.2%). 34.2% of small businesses are engaged in agriculture, 12.7% in industry, 11.6% in construction, 13.4% in trade and 28.1% in services. (6)

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As can be seen from the cross-sectional analysis of the above items, we can see a relatively low level of small business in an industrial sector where the efficiency of job creation compared to other sectors is high. Maintaining the current growth rate of this indicator may lead to problems in the future with the increase in wages and real incomes of the population from entrepreneurial activities. This situation may lead to the restriction of social guarantees provided by the state to the population. In addition, the share of the number of small businesses in trade remains high. In the retail trade turnover, we can see that the share of small businesses and micro-firms was 20.2%, while the share of individual entrepreneurs was 69.4%, which has a negative impact on cash inflows to the banking sector. and inconsistencies in the taxable base of small businesses.

As a result of radical reforms to support entrepreneurs and improve the business environment, Uzbekistan has risen 7 places to 69th place in the World Bank's Doing Business 2020 report and is ranked among the top 20 in the world. (7) For the first time, our country has risen to eighth place in the world in terms of ease of opening a new enterprise. As a result of such opportunities, 91,000 new business entities have been established in the last 10 months of this year, or twice as many as in 2018. (8) However, it should be noted that much remains to be done to develop the sector. In particular, it is necessary to address the shortcomings identified in the report "Doing Business - 2020", including the creation of facilities for land allocation, construction and registration of property. Therefore, it is necessary to provide entrepreneurs with land through online auctions, to ensure the interdepartmental electronic exchange of information on property registration. Based on foreign experience, it is also important to establish a separate structure responsible for the independent transfer of property rights from the state register.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In summary, increasing the contribution of small business to the country's economy, creating small industrial zones, improving the investment climate and competitive environment, expanding public procurement in the framework of public-private partnerships with small businesses, We can see this through the strengthening of mutually beneficial cooperation, the involvement of business entities in the innovation process. It should be noted that financial support for successful and promising small enterprises that have sufficient export potential, but at the same time do not have sufficient capital for further development, is of great importance. These measures will help to create more jobs in the field of effective small business, increase access to world markets, increase the country's export potential and increase incomes.

In short, the development of entrepreneurship and small business in our country today remains one of the priorities of public policy. In the words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, we can achieve development and a prosperous life only through active entrepreneurship, hard work and aspiration.

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